

Behaviour determines invasion ability: Postural control of water loss in painted reed frogs

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Background

Painted reed frogs (*Hyperolius marmoratus* Rapp) invaded the temperate, winter-rainfall regions of the south-western Cape, South Africa, from 1997. They have overcome a significant natural barrier by expanding their range from summer/aseasonal to winter rainfall regions. At the organism level, this capacity could be related to behaviour, physiology or life history traits.

Breeding phenology is unchanged, and frogs breed during the dry summer¹ as opposed to the wet summer in the historical range. This requires the frogs to be active during periods of low humidity and high evaporative and heat stress.

We aimed to establish whether painted reed frogs show phenotypic plasticity of metabolism and water loss that allow them to exploit these novel habitats.

Methods

Metabolic and water loss rates of resting and active adult frogs were measured during 2011 and 2012 using standard respirometry methods^{2,3}. Animals were acclimated to 3 temperatures commonly encountered in their historical and novel ranges.

Key findings

Resting frogs (photos b-d)

Metabolic rate is lower in warm-acclimated than in cool-acclimated frogs (compensatory acclimation⁴).

Frogs acclimated at the highest temperature have lowest thermal sensitivity of metabolic rate to temperature.

Water loss rate does not respond to acclimation or test temperature, indicating little plasticity in this trait.

Active frogs (photo a)

Warm-acclimated animals perform better under warm conditions, having lower metabolic rates at the highest test temperature.

Water loss is highly sensitive to test temperature in active frogs.

Metabolic and water loss rates are more sensitive to acclimation treatment at the highest test temperature.

Conclusions

The water-conserving position of resting painted reed frogs (minimum surface area exposure by tucking of head, limbs and phalanges) allows them to maintain constant water loss despite the positive effects of temperature on metabolic rate.

This adaptation to savanna habitats⁵ likely facilitates the establishment of these frogs in the water-scarce shrublands of the Fynbos biome (c.f. ref.⁶ for coqui frogs in sub-tropical wet forests).

Plasticity of metabolic and water loss rates in active frogs likely provides a mechanism by which *H. marmoratus* remains active during warm, dry conditions in the novel range.

References: ¹ Tyson *Climatic change and variability in southern Africa* (OUP 1986); ² Withers *Aust J Zool*, 49, 445-461 (2001); ³ Lighton *Measuring metabolic rates: A manual for scientists* (OUP 2008); ⁴ Rome *et al.* in *Environmental Physiology of the Amphibians* (UCP1992); ⁵ Schmuck & Linsenmair *Comp. Biochem. Phys. A* 118, 1335-1352 (1997); ⁶ Pough *et al.* *Ecology*, 64, 244-252 (1983).

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